

EFFECTS OF DIETARY INCLUSION OF KIGELIA AFRICANA FRUIT AND LEAF MEALS ON LIBIDO AND FERTILITY INDICES IN RABBITS

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ABSTRACT

Sexual performance is essential for reproductive efficiency in animal production because it influences mating behaviour, hormone secretion, conception rate, and overall herd productivity. A 12-week feeding trial was conducted at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm to evaluate the effects of dietary *Kigelia africana* leaf and fruit meals on libido and fertility indices of rabbits. A total of 108 rabbits (70 days old), comprising males and females in a 2:1 ratio, were randomly allotted to nine treatments (12 rabbits per treatment) in a $2 \times 4 + 1$ factorial arrangement. The first factor was plant part (leaf or fruit), while the second factor was inclusion level (5, 10, 15, and 20%). The eight factorial combinations were compared with a basal diet without *Kigelia* as a control. Plant part had no significant effect on the reproductive hormones measured; however, inclusion level significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and testosterone in bucks, particularly at 20%. Does feeding fruit meal show higher FSH than those fed leaf meal? Libido improved with *Kigelia* supplementation, as reaction time was shorter in bucks fed fruit meal (15.65 s) and decreased significantly with increasing inclusion level. The control group recorded the longest reaction time (37.25 s), while 20% inclusion produced one of the shortest values (17.50 s). Conception rate was significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced by inclusion level, with 15% and 20% diets achieving 100% conception. Does fed fruit meal had higher litter size (6.68), and litter size increased with higher inclusion levels, reaching 7.81 at the upper levels. Overall, dietary *K. africana* improved libido and fertility in rabbits, with fruit meal producing superior results compared with leaf meal. Higher inclusion levels (15–20%) enhanced reproductive hormones, reduced reaction time, increased conception rate, and improved litter size, indicating better reproductive performance.

Key words: Fertility, Libido, Rabbit, Hormone, *Kigelia africana*

INTRODUCTION

Kigelia africana, commonly called cucumber tree is a member to Bignoniaceae family, distributed in tropical West, East, and Central Africa, with a notable presence in the lowland plains of Nigeria. (Ogbeche, et al., 2002). It is usually planted for ornamental purposes because of its decorative flowers and its unusual fruit. The fruit is a woody and fibrous berry that suspends from a long fibrous stalk. In the wild, the fruits are eaten by mammals such as hippopotamus, monkeys, giraffes, baboons, bush pigs, savannah elephant and so on (Joffe, 2003). Among the folkloric medical practitioners, *Kigelia africana* fruit symbolizes fertility (Burkill, 1985), they make use of different parts soaked in alcohol or water for treatment of various fertility related problems (Ogbeche et al., 2002). It is traditionally used to manage other ailments, including retained placenta, postpartum hemorrhage, dizziness and as anti-cancer agent (Gill 1992). In South western Nigeria, the bark extract is commonly used for its aphrodisiac effect as it enhances sexual libido and erection in males (Dasofunjo, et al., 2024). Over the years, the plants have been used for management and treatment of many ailments in humans, however, its application is gradually gaining grounds in animal nutrition. The application of *Kigelia africana* fruit meals was well documented in fish (Adeparusi et al. 2010) up to 15%, and in rabbit up to 10% (Adeyemi et al. 2022) dietary inclusions. The availability and affordability in areas where they are abundant, could help in mitigating the problems of high cost of animal feed. In

animal production, the role of these ethnobotanical plants cannot be over emphasized, they serve as possible sources of food/nutrients as they supply some of the essential nutrient (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2022) requirements of farm animals at a low price due to their minimal competition with man. Additionally, they serve as therapeutic agents boosting reproductive performance as well the overall health of the animals due to their high antioxidant levels (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2022). Their appropriate inclusion in the diets could help reduce the cost of production, and also reducing the competition between man and animal for feed ingredients.

The use of *K. africana* in rabbit feed is not limited to reduction in the cost of feeding but also can solve some of the problems associated with rabbit farming, one of which is inconsistent libido (shy rabbit). Therefore, the need to establish the level of safe use of KA meals becomes a necessity, hence this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal managements and experimental layout

The experimental trial was conducted at the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm.

A total of 108 rabbits of 70 days old were used for this experiment. Rabbits were randomly assigned to nine treatments (12 rabbits per treatment) in a $2 \times 4 + 1$ factorial arrangement. The first factor was plant parts consisting of two levels (fruit or leaf) while the second factor was inclusion levels

(5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%) plus 0%. The control diet (0% inclusion) was common to both plant parts and treated as a baseline in the factorial model as presented in Table 1. Rabbits were housed individually and had access to feed and water *ad libitum*. The experiment lasted for twelve (12) weeks and was conducted with the approval of the University of Ilorin Ethical Review Committee (protocol identification code: UERC/AGR/084).

Preparation of experimental diet

The *Kigelia africana* fruits and leaf were collected from Ikotun, Oyun local government area of Kwara State. The fruits and leaf were cleaned and fruits were chopped into smaller pieces to allow drying and easy processing. They were air-dried until constant weight was obtained and thereafter milled with a milling machine into powder which was incorporated into the experimental diet. Independent diets were formulated from the fruit and leaf (5%, 10%, 15%, 20% plus 0%).

Libido performance of rabbit fed *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals

Libido, intromission (thrusting), and fertility performances were used to measure reproductive responses of rabbits in this study.

Six weeks into the experiment, the libido of bucks and does was assessed. Bucks were closely observed for pubertal signs and reproductive alertness by introducing a doe of the same treatment group. Reaction time in bucks and receptivity in does were recorded in seconds, following the method of Gado *et al.* (2015). This procedure was

repeated at 18 and 22 weeks of age.

Hormone analysis of rabbit buck and does

Blood samples were collected from eight rabbits per treatment after eight weeks of the feeding trial. This was done early in the morning before feeding. Rabbits were restrained, and blood was drawn from the ear vein using a disposable syringe and needle into sterilized plastic plain tubes. The samples were used to determine reproductive hormone levels, including follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), testosterone, progesterone, and luteinizing hormone (LH), using ELISA kits for hormonal assay as described by Kumar *et al.* (2018).

Fertility performance of rabbits fed *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals

Rabbit does and bucks of same treatment were crossed using natural mating in a ratio 2:1 (at 26 weeks old). The mating dates were noted for each does to determine the gestation periods. Conception was confirmed in does after ten days and up to fourteen days after mating through palpation. Parturition date, litter size, birth weight of kids, abnormalities in kids, mortality rate and gestation period were noted for each doe. The kid birth weights (gram) were taken using a sensitive digital scale (Electronic scale, Model EHA251) delete.

Table 1. Composition of Experimental Diets Supplemented with *Kigelia africana* Fruit/Leaf Meals

Ingredients	0 %	5 %	10 %	15 %	20 %	5 %	10 %	15 %	20 %
	Control	Fruit	fruit	Fruit	Fruit	Leaf	Leaf	Leaf	leaf
Maize	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00
Soyabean Meal	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
Wheat Offal	12.00	14.00	10.00	10.00	5.00	14.00	12.00	9.00	11.00
Maize offal	7.00	5.00	5.00	7.00	11.00	10.00	5.00	10.00	5.00
Rice husk	27.00	22.00	21.00	14.00	10.00	21.00	19.00	12.00	10.00
Fish Meal	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
KAM	0.00	5.00	10.00	15.00	20.00	5.00	10.00	15.00	20.00
Salt	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Dicalcium phosphate	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lysine	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Premix	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Total	100								
Analyzed Nutrients									
Crude protein, %	15.94	16.06	16.36	16.10	16.12	15.80	15.62	15.59	16.23
Crude Fibre, %	11.62	11.71	11.88	11.80	11.60	11.80	11.72	11.85	11.82
Ether Extract, %	4.50	4.0	4.39	5.0	4.56	5.0	4.54	4.90	4.98
Calculated ME(Kcal/kg)	2,417.10	2,366.83	2,386.66	2,347.39	2,312.82	2,349.67	2,308.83	2,300.50	2,300.16

*KAM= *Kigelia africana* meals, ME= Metabolizable energy

Statistical analysis of data collected

All data collected from hormone analysis, buck mounting reaction time, doe receptivity, and fertility performance were subjected to a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedure following a model for $2 \times 4 + 1$ factorial design (Steel and Torrie, 1980). Data from each group were analyzed using General Linear Model procedure SAS Institute (2002), and significant differences between treatments means were separated using the Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955).

RESULTS

Results of selected hormones of rabbits fed *K. africana* fruit and leaf meal are presented in tables 2 and 3. The *K. africana* parts had no significant effects ($p > 0.05$) on the reproductive hormones in buck. The inclusion level factor however influenced ($p < 0.05$) their concentrations. Testosterone and FSH concentrations increased as increasing level of the *K. africana* meals. LH concentration was higher in rabbit fed 5% *K. africana*. In the does, there was also a significant effect on the hormonal concentrations, the fruit meal significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) the level of FSH

compared with those on the leaf. However, the *K. africana* parts were not significant factor ($p > 0.05$) for LH and progesterone concentrations. At the inclusion levels, the concentration of all the reproductive hormones measured increased as the treatment level increased. The details of interactions between *K. africana* parts and inclusion for LH which was the only significant parameter are presented in Table 3a.

Table 3a showed the summary of the interaction between *K. africana* parts and inclusion levels for serum Luteinizing hormone of rabbit does. This table showed the clear interactions between the factors evaluated, regardless of the *K. africana* parts the concentrations of LH remained same at 10%, 15% and 20% inclusion. However, at 5% inclusion, LH concentration was significantly increased ($p > 0.05$) in rabbit does fed *K. africana* fruit meal compared with those on the leaf of the same group. The LH concentration obtained at 10%, 15% and 20% were statistically ($p < 0.05$) the same but different from the control.

Table 2. Reproductive Hormones response of Rabbits Bucks fed *Kigelia africana* Fruit and Leaf Meals

KA Parts	FSH (ng/mL)	LH (mIU/mL)	TESTOSTERONE (ng/mL)
Fruit	121.86	1.72	73.33
Leaf	122.83	1.81	69.51
P-value	0.92	0.48	0.11
Inclusion Levels, %			
0	100.29 ^b	1.58 ^{bc}	54.82 ^c
5	114.53 ^{ab}	2.03 ^a	75.12 ^b
10	119.80 ^{ab}	1.49 ^c	73.55 ^b
15	133.03 ^{ab}	1.98 ^{ab}	67.91 ^b
20	144.09 ^a	1.77 ^{ab}	85.70 ^a
P-value	0.05	0.04	0.01
Parts*Levels	*	*	*
P-value	0.74	0.13	0.55
±SEM	6.84	0.09	1.62

KA= *Kigelia africana*, a, b, c – means with different superscripts are significant along the column, S – significant, NS – not-significant, SEM= Standard Error of Mean

Table 3. Reproductive Hormones response of Rabbits Does fed *K. africana* Fruit and Leaf Meals

KA Parts	FSH (ng/mL)	LH (mIU/mL)	PROGESTERONE (ng/mL)
Fruit	105.39 ^a	1.70	14.52
Leave	89.23 ^b	1.57	14.40
P-value	0.03	0.31	0.76
Inclusion Levels (%)			
0	85.76 ^c	1.49 ^b	12.95 ^{bc}
5	109.35 ^b	1.73 ^{ab}	12.29 ^c
10	104.4 ^{bc}	1.78 ^{ab}	15.39 ^a
15	120.28 ^{ab}	1.88 ^a	14.15 ^{ab}
20	129.33 ^a	1.88 ^a	15.52 ^a
P-value	0.04	0.01	0.002
Parts*Levels	NS	*	NS
P-value	0.07	0.007	0.56
±SEM	4.92	0.08	0.28

KA= *Kigelia africana*, a, b, c – means with different superscripts are significant along the column, * – significant, NS – Not-significant, SEM= Standard Error of Meal

Table 3a. Interactions between KA Parts and Inclusion Levels for Luteinizing Hormone of Rabbits Fed *Kigelia africana* Fruit and Leaf Meals

Inclusion Levels (%)						
KA Parts	0%	5%	10%	15%	20%	±SEM
Fruit	0.91 ^b	1.99 ^a	1.95 ^a	1.67 ^{ab}	1.99 ^a	0.20
Leaf	0.91 ^b	0.86 ^b	2.19 ^a	1.92 ^a	1.99 ^a	0.20

KA= *Kigelia africana*, a, b, c– means with different superscript are significant along the row, SEM=Standard Error of Mean

Table 4 showed the mounting reactions time exhibited by rabbit bucks fed *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals. The reaction time of rabbit bucks fed leaf was significantly ($p < 0.05$) longer than those fed fruit at both 18 and 22 weeks of age. Considering the inclusion levels, the control had the longest reaction time while the shortest time was recorded in the groups fed 20% inclusion. This was a case of reduction of reaction time with increasing levels of KA meals. The period between mounting and fall-off (thrusting) was statistically the same in all the groups. The detail of interaction for the significant

parameters were presented in the interaction table.

Table 4a presents the details of interaction between *Kigelia africana* parts (fruit or leaf) and inclusion levels for bucks' reaction time at 18 weeks of age. The control group had the highest ($p < 0.05$) reaction time. The shortest reaction time was noted in bucks fed 20% *Kigelia africana* fruit meal. However, at 20%, fruit inclusion significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowered the reaction time of the buck compared with those on the leaf meal showing a positive impact on their libido.

Table 4. Mounting Reaction Time of Rabbit Bucks fed *Kigelia africana* Fruit and Leaf Meals

KA parts	BRT at 18weeks (seconds)	BRT at 22weeks (seconds)	Thrusting period (seconds)
Fruit	21.65 ^b	14.60 ^b	4.95
Leaf	25.65 ^a	16.10 ^a	5.10
P-value	0.002	0.05	0.46
Inclusion levels (%)			
0	37.25 ^a	33.25 ^a	4.50
5	23.00 ^b	13.25 ^b	4.50
10	19.88 ^{bc}	10.63 ^c	4.63
15	20.63 ^{bc}	10.25 ^c	4.75
20	17.50 ^c	9.38 ^c	4.98
P-value	0.01	0.001	0.06
Parts*Inclusion Levels	*	NS	NS
P-value	0.02	0.79	0.91
±SEM	0.83	0.52	0.14

KA= *Kigelia africana*, a, b, c – means with different superscript are significant along the column, BRT – Buck Reaction Time, *- significant, NS – Not-significant, SEM=Standard Error of Mean

Table 4a. Interactions between KA Parts and Inclusion Levels on Rabbit Buck Reaction Time at 18 weeks

KA Parts	Inclusion Level, %					
	0%	5%	10%	15%	20%	SEM
Fruit	37.25 ^a	23.25 ^b	18.50 ^b	17.50 ^{bc}	11.75 ^c	1.86
Leaf	37.25 ^a	22.75 ^b	21.25 ^b	23.75 ^b	23.25 ^b	1.86

KA= *Kigelia africana*, a, b, c – means with different superscript are significant along the row, SEM=Standard Error of Mean

The receptivity of rabbit does to bucks are presented in table 5. There was a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the acceptability of does fed *Kigelia africana* fruit meal at 18 weeks of age. The percentage of receptive does were also higher in the same group. *Kigelia africana* parts had no significant influence ($p > 0.05$) on both the receptivity time and percentage of receptive does at 22 weeks of age. At inclusion levels, the receptiveness of the does were not

significantly affected ($p > 0.05$), however, percentage receptive does increased as the levels of *Kigelia africana* meals increased. Conception of the does was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased with fruit meal inclusion. Similarly, the level of inclusion of the treatments significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced the conception percentage. It increased as the level of *Kigelia africana* meals increased.

Table 5. Receptivity of Rabbit Does Fed *Kigelia africana* Fruit and Leaf meals

KA Parts	Receptivity at 18 weeks (second)	% Receptivity at 18 weeks	Receptivity at 22 weeks, second	% Receptivity at 22 weeks	Conception (%)
Fruit	5.58 ^b	65.00 ^b	8.93	95.00	92.50 ^a
Leaf	9.25 ^a	72.50 ^a	10.68	95.00	90.00 ^b
P-value	0.01	0.01	0.12	-	0.0001
Treatment levels (%)					
0	8.25	50.00 ^d	10.88	87.50 ^b	75.00 ^c
5	7.56	62.50 ^c	9.69	87.50 ^b	81.30 ^b
10	6.63	62.50 ^c	9.19	100 ^a	100 ^a
15	8.25	75.00 ^b	10.56	100 ^a	100 ^a
20	8.38	93.75 ^a	8.69	100 ^a	100 ^a
P-value	0.84	0.01	0.71	0.01	0.001
Type*Levels	NS	NS	NS	-	*
P-value	0.74	0.77	0.77	-	0.0001
±SEM	1.01	0.004	0.79	0.002	0.002

a, b, c – means with different superscript are significant along the column, * – significant, NS – Not-significant

The reproductive responses of rabbit does fed *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meal are shown in table 6. The inclusion of the *Kigelia africana* parts had no significantly ($p>0.05$) influence on the gestation periods, birth weights of the kids, mortality and kits'

abnormality. However, litter size was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher in does fed fruit meals. Similarly, it also increased with increasing levels of KA meals with 15% and 20% having the highest.

Table 6. Fertility Performance of Rabbit Does Fed *Kigelia africana* Fruit and Leaf Meals

KA Parts	Gestation period (days)	Litter size (no)	Birth weight (g)	Mortality (%)	Abnormality (%)
Fruit	30.63	6.68 ^a	41.59	0.73	0.00
Leaf	30.78	6.10 ^b	42.22	0.53	0.00
P-value	0.51	0.03	0.45	0.18	0.00
Inclusion Levels (%)					
0	30.88	4.25 ^d	42.58	0.75	0.00
5	30.38	6.13 ^c	43.00	0.63	0.00
10	31.19	6.63 ^b	43.23	0.50	0.00
15	30.63	7.13 ^{ab}	43.40	0.56	0.00
20	30.44	7.81 ^a	42.77	0.68	0.00
P-value	0.16	0.01	0.06	0.84	-
Parts*Levels	NS	*	NS	NS	-
P-value	0.45	0.46	0.81	0.65	0.00
±SEM	0.16	0.11	1.37	0.10	0.00

a, b, c, d – means with different superscript are significant along the column, no - number, * - significant, NS - Not significant

DISCUSSION

Onset of puberty and the level of sexual drive (libido) are vital physiological trait in a successful rabbit production. Fighting, mounting of objects, spraying of urine, growling, circling, territorial biting, destructive chewing and digging (in females) are major characteristic signs of puberty attainment in rabbit. In this present study, mounting and thrusting were the major tools used for evaluation. The bucks on *K. africana* (KA) fruit and leaf presented higher sex drive related to the control group. The reaction time of the bucks fed diets containing KA meals were significantly reduced at earlier age compared with the control. This is an indication that KA was able to bring the rabbit on puberty earlier. This can be corroborated with report of Micheli *et al.* (2020) who reported a positive effect of *K. africana* fruit extract on reproductive performance of rats, emphasizing on its effect on earlier onset of sexual maturation, suggesting androgenic activity. Moreso, the low reaction times observed at 15% and 20% fruit inclusion, suggested that KA part was a significant factor for libido performance, with fruit having a better results compared with the leaf. Moreover, various factors have been identified as key, responsible for libido, fertility and overall reproductive performance among which is testosterone concentration in males. Coincidentally, serum testosterone levels of rabbits in treated groups were also higher. This study also revealed that KA fruit meal as well as higher inclusions had a

significant influence on the libido of the buck at younger age. This is corroborated with report of (Abillo *et al.* (2025), who worked on the effect of first mating on reproductive performance of dam. , This is suggesting that KA fruit and leaf meals have ability to influence pubertal attainment in rabbits as it was observed in this study.

Enhanced libido observed from this study could be attributed to Testosterone, acting synergistically with follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH), which is key to pubertal development in male animals. This result is in line with report of Momo *et al.* (2020) who used *Triumfetta rhomboidea* leaf extract in male guinea pigs and reported high level of serum testosterone which he also described as essential element for normal sex drive and libido. In this study, hormonal profiles assessed at the pubertal stage revealed a progressive increase in reproductive hormone concentrations with increasing dietary inclusion levels of KA fruit and leaf meals. This response may be attributed to the presence of essential nutrients and bioactive phytochemicals with antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2022), which are known to enhance weight gain and overall physiological performance in rabbits. Improved nutritional status has been widely reported to have positive influence on testicular growth and function, ultimately leading to enhanced reproductive performance (Ewuola and Olujimi, 2019, Attia and Kamel, 2012).

The phytochemical constituents of *KA* meals, particularly flavonoids (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2022), may have exerted stimulatory effects on hormonal responses in rabbits, given their protective role on Leydig and Sertoli cells, which are essential for testosterone production and spermatogenesis.

The testosterone concentrations recorded in the present study were higher than those reported by Gado *et al.* (2015) in mature rabbits fed multi-enzyme-based diets. Such variations may be influenced by several factors beyond nutrition, notably the use of antioxidant-rich feed components capable of mitigating oxidative stress, a known constraint to reproductive performance in both animals and humans. The antioxidant potential of *KA* fruit and leaf meals can therefore be attributed to the synergistic effects of vitamin E, zinc, flavonoids, and other bioactive compounds present, all of which are established antioxidant agents (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2022).

The reaction time reported from this study was longer but close to 4.2s reported by Ogbuewu *et al.* (2009) and shorter than 14–21s reported by Saafa *et al.* (2008), and 22.31s reported by Gado *et al.* (2015). These differences observed could be due to the high concentration of testosterone reported in this study, which is associated with male maturity and pubertal characteristics. This increased concentration could be linked to presence of bioactive compounds and

phytochemicals in *KA* which possesses antioxidant properties. Antioxidants have been reported to have a great influence on sexual drive and overall reproductive health (Ranjith *et al.* 2025). Good sex drive (libido) of rabbit bucks is essential to achieve maximum productivity in breeding especially through natural mating (Saleh *et al.* 2010).

The reproductive performance of rabbit does in this study showed that the inclusion of *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals had a significant positive influence on the litter size. This was observed with a correspondent increased level of *KA* meals. Physiologically, higher number in litter size implies that multiple eggs have been released by the does, this suggested that *KA* might have some super ovulatory effects on the rabbit does and this may be corroborated with their usage by the traditional healers to treat infertility in man and woman of child bearing age, (Ogbeche *et al.*, 2002). It could also be associated with antioxidant potential possessed by *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals as reported by Aliyu and Adeyina, (2022).

According to Wang *et al.* (2017), the reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced during ovarian physiological metabolism is maintained with the help of antioxidant thereby ensuring oocyte maturation, ovulation, fertilization, implantation and embryo development without damage by these free radicals.

CONCLUSION

Kigelia africana fruit and leaf meals inclusions up to 20% improved the libido and reproductive performance of rabbit. It can also be concluded that KA meals can be positively influence pubertal attainment at earlier age in rabbit. Specifically, the fruit meal improved reproductive hormone production and subsequently libido and

fertility performance better. Based on the result obtained from this research and previous (Aliyu and Adeyina, 2025), 15% inclusion of *K. africana* meals is recommended in the diets of rabbits meant for breeding purpose. However, long-term and toxicological studies are required

REFERENCES

- Abilio P. C, Leonel A. J, Hermenegilda P. D, Milton P.M, Tiago P.G, Manuel G-Herreros, and Custódio G.B (2025). Age at first mating and season of dam birth affect reproductive and productive traits of Mozambican Angoni cattle. *Translational Animal Science*, 9, t x a f 1 3 0 <https://doi.org/10.1093/tas/txaf130>
- Adeparusi, E. O, Dada, A. A and Alele, O. V (2010). Effects of Medicinal Plant (Kigelia Africana) on Sperm Quality of African Catfish *Clarias Gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) Broodstock. *Journal of Agriculture*.2:1, 193-199.
- Adeyemi K. D, Akinfenwa O. A, Atolani O., Shittu R. M, Adeyina A. O, and Aliyu K. I (2022). Growth Performance, Carcass Traits, Muscle Fatty Acids, Intramuscular Fat, Cholesterol, and Antioxidant Status in Rabbits Supplemented with Kigelia pinnata Leaf Meal. *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol* Pp 1-9.
- Aliyu K. I and Adeyina A. O (2022). Phytochemical, vitamin compositions and antioxidant potential of *Kigelia africana* fruit and leaf meals. *Asian Journal of Advances in Research* 5(1): 664-667.
- Aliyu K.I and Adeyina A.O (2025). Effect of *Kigelia africana* Leaf and Fruit Meals on Blood Parameters of Rabbits. *International Journal of Advancing Research, Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. Vol 1(1):1-6.
- Attia Y.A, and Kamel K.I (2012). Semen quality, testosterone, seminal plasma biochemical and antioxidant profiles of rabbit bucks fed diets supplemented with different concentrations of soybean lecithin. *Animal*.6(5):824-833.
- Burkill, H.M. (1985). The useful plants of west tropical Africa. *Planta WT Afr.*, 1: 254-257.
- Dasofunjo K., Ugwu M. N., Okafor A. I., Ujong U. P., and Ati B. U (2024). Spermatogenic and Libido Enhancing Effect of Ethanol Extract of Kigelia Africana in $\Delta 9$ Tetrahydrocannabinol Induced Erectile Dysfunction in Male Wistar Rats. *Journal: African Journal of Biology and Medical Research (AJBMR)* Volume/Issue: Volume 7, Issue 4 31-57. DOI: 10.52589/AJBMR-PUZG3DRP
- Duncan, D. B. (1955). *Multiple range and multiple F tests*. *Biometrics*, 11(1), 1–42.
- Ewuola, E. O., and Olujimi, A. T. (2019). Bovine testicular fluid enhanced growth performance of broiler chickens. *Nigerian Journal of Animal Production*, 46 (1) , 1 8 8 – 1 9 5 . <https://doi.org/10.51791/njap.v46i1.1287>
- Gado, H., Mellado, M., Salem, A.Z.M., Zaragoza, A., and Seleem, T.S.T. (2015). Semen characteristics, sexual hormones and libido of Hy-Plus rabbit bucks influenced by a dietary multi-enzyme additive. *World Rabbit Science*, 23, 111–120. doi:10.4995/wrs.2015.3464
- Gill, L.S. (1992). Ethnomedical uses of plants in Nigeria. *Uniben Press, Benin City*. pp: 143
- Joffe, P. (2003). “*Kigelia africana* (Lam) Benth”, Pretoria National Botanical Garden.
- Kumar, A., Singh, S. P., and Singh, R. (2018). Effects of phytoadditives on

- reproductive hormones and antioxidant status in rabbits. *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition*, 102(2), 575–583.
- Micheli V, Sanogo R, Mobilia MA, and Occhiuto F (2020). Effects of *Kigelia africana* (Lam.) Benth. fruits extract on the development and maturation of the reproductive system in immature male rats. *Nat Prod Res.* 34(1):162-166. doi: 10.1080/14786419.2019.157
- Momo, A., Obianime, A. W., Uche, F. I., Berebon, D. P., and Odimegwu, D. C. A. (2020). *Aqueous extract of Triumfetta rhomboidea Jacq leaves modulates hormones and upregulates male fertility function in guinea pig. Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.13005/bpj/1980> 9809.
- Ogbeche, K.A., Ogunbiyi, Y.O and Duru, F.I.O. (2002). Effect of Methanol extract of *Kigelia africana* on Sperm Motility and Fertility in Rats. *Nig J Health and BiomedSci*, 1 (2): 113-116.
- Ogbuewu, I.P., Okoli, I.C., and Iloeje, M.U. (2009). Semen quality characteristics, reaction time, testis weight and seminiferous tubule diameter of buck rabbits fed neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) leaf meal-based diets. *Iranian J. Reprod. Med.*, 7: 23-28
- Ranjith R.1, Samir B, Taylor P.K, and Larry E. M (2025). Antioxidant Supplementation for Erectile Dysfunction: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Double-Blind, Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trials. *World J. Mens Health.* 43(1):81-91. DOI: 10.5534/wjmh.230280
- Safaa, H.M., Emarah, M.E., and Saleh N.F.A. (2008). Seasonal effects on semen quality in Black Baladi and white New Zealand rabbit bucks. *World Rabbit Sci.*, 16: 13-20. DOI: 10.4995/wrs.2008.640
- Saleh, S.Y., Attia, K.A., Fouad, M., and Nassar. M.M. (2010). Effects of Multi-enzyme Feed Additive “Kemzyme” or/and Sodium Bentonite “as a Feed Binder” on Sexual Activity and Some Fertility Parameters of Rabbit Bucks. *J. Agr. Sci.*, 2: 89-99. DOI: 10.5539/jas.v2n4p89
- SAS Institute Inc. (2002). SAS/STAT User's guide, version 8 for windows. SAS institute Inc., SAS campus drive, Cary, North.
- Steel, R. G., and Torrie, J. H. (1980). Principles and procedures of statistics. *Principle and procedures of statistics.*
- Wang S, Zhou X, Sun Y, and Junjie M, (2017). The Role of Antioxidant Enzymes in the Ovaries. *Journal Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity.*
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